

transplanting in mid-Aug, the second in the first week of Sep, the third in mid-Sep, and the fourth (only on late-transplanted crops) in the first week of Oct.

Periodic incidence of adults on the leaves indicated successive broods. Grubs mined between the leaf epidermis, turning 1/3 to 1/2 white. At late-stage infestation, fields developed a blighted

look. Early generations caused patchy damage but cumulative damage by successive generations covered whole fields. Crop-cuts (10 m²) were taken from short-duration Ratna and long-duration Pankaj. Yield loss was 23% for short-duration and 17% for long-duration varieties.

Weather conditions may have encouraged the hispa outbreaks. Most

days were rainy during sowing, which prevented the normal dry seeding. Rainfall was higher than normal, but the number of rainy days and the duration of bright sunshine hours were the same. Sunny weather interrupted by quick showers. no summer plowing, and lack of insecticide application may have increased hispa incidence.✍

Virulence of green leafhopper (GLH) colonies from Luzon, Philippines, on IR36 and IR42

H. R. Rapusas and E.A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, IRRI

In 1979, we surveyed farmers' fields in the Philippines to determine if there were GLH *Nephotettix virescens* biotypes virulent on the resistant varieties being grown. Results generally indicated that biotypes were not a problem. We repeated the survey in several Luzon provinces in 1984.

GLH adults were collected in Nueva Ecija, Tarlac, Pangasinan, La Union, Ilocos Sur, Ilocos Norte, and Abra and grouped by towns and varieties from which they were collected. Ten colonies were reared on susceptible TN1 in the greenhouse for two generations. A TN1 colony maintained in the greenhouse for more than 50 generations was included in the test. We tested the ability of each colony to develop a population on resistant IR36 and IR42.

Six-day-old seedlings of the test varieties were transplanted at 5 seedlings per pot in 10-cm-diameter clay pots. Two weeks after transplanting, each pot was enclosed in a mylar film cage to keep out other insect pests, parasites, and predators. Ten days later, the plants were inspected and any arthropods present in the cage were removed. Three pair of 3-d-old GLH adults from each of 11 colonies were introduced in each cage, replicated 5 times. The surviving insects were counted 25 d later.

A colony that was significantly bigger than the greenhouse colony on IR36 or IR42 indicated an increase in virulence of that colony (see table). Colonies from all locations except Cuyapo. Nueva

Populations of GLH colonies from Luzon, Philippines, when reared on IR36 and IR42.

Colony	Variety from which collected	Progeny/3 females ^a on	
		IR36	IR42
Capas, Tarlac	IR36	130 abcd	131 ab
Guimba, Nueva Ecija	IR36	164 bcd	204 bc
Cuyapo, Nueva Ecija	IR42	91 abc	178 bc
Umingan, Pangasinan	IR42	152 bcd	127 ab
Santo Tomas-San Jose, Nueva Ecija	IR42	207 d	227 c
Bauang, La Union	IR42, IR36, traditional	143 bcd	472 d
San Fernando-Bacnotan, La Union	IR36, IR42, traditional	109 abc	221 c
Santa Cruz-Bantay, Ilocos Sur	IR42, traditional	176 cd	162 bc
Paoay-Badoc, Ilocos Norte	IR42, Wagwag	152 bcd	155 abc
Pidigan, Abra	IR42	82 ab	184 bc
Greenhouse	TN1	57 a	89 a

^a Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Ecija; San Fernando-Bacnotan. La Union; and Pidigan, Abra, were more virulent on IR36 than the greenhouse colony. On IR42, all colonies except those from Capas, Tarlac; Umingan, Pangasinan; and Paoay-Badoc, Ilocos Norte, were more virulent than the greenhouse colony.

In contrast to our 1979 survey, results indicate that GLH colonies collected in most of the provinces were more virulent than the greenhouse colony.

Populations were about double those of the greenhouse colony on both IR36 and IR42. Therefore, GLH biotypes are developing in the Philippines.

Because IR36 and IR42 have low level of resistance to tungro virus (RTV), but have resistance to the vector GLH, there is the potential for higher RTV incidence on IR36 and IR42 in the locations where GLH colonies are most virulent.✍

Influence of planting time and rainfall on gall midge (GM) incidence and rice yield in Goa, India

D. Sundararaju, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex for Goa, Ela, Old Goa, India

We assessed damage caused by GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) and its impact on grain yield in 1981 and 1982. Jaya was planted at 2-wk intervals in 40-m² plots with 5 replications beginning in Jun and ending in Jul. No insecticide was applied. GM damage was recorded 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT)

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1. GM population and rainfall pattern at Goa, India, 1981.

2. Relation between GM infestation and grain yield at Goa, India, 1981.

and at harvest. Rainfall and daily light trap catches of GM were recorded from Jun to Oct 1981 (Fig. 1).

The early planted crop had no GM damage up to 45 DT, and GM infestation later had minimal impact on grain yield. GM attacked late-planted crops at 30 DT and significantly reduced yield (see table). GM infestation at 30 DT in 1981 was significantly and negatively correlated with grain yield ($r = -0.694$) (Fig. 2).

Peak GM population was in Sep. about 2 mo after peak rainfall, which may indicate probable GM outbreak. Therefore, rice planted early (Jun) in the monsoon has better chance of escaping infestation than late crops.

GM infestation and grain yield of different plantings, Goa, India,^a 1981.

Planting date	Silvershoot (%)						Grain yield (t/ha)	
	30 DT		45 DT		75 DT		1980	1981
	1980	1981	1980	1981	1980	1981		
7 Jun	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	6.9 a	5.1 a
22 Jun	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	15 b	6.2 a	4.7 b
7 Jul	0 a	3 b	6 b	30 b	23 c	20 c	4.7 b	3.2 c
22 Jul	6 b	23 c	15 c	32 b	11 b	29 d	4.2 b	1.6 d

^a Separation of means in a column at 5 % level.

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Oviposition of rice whorl maggot (RWM) in wet seedbeds

J. P. Bandong and J. A. Litsinger,
Entomology Department, IRRI

RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino is a major pest of irrigated rice in central Luzon, Philippines. Farmers often spray their wet seedbeds several times, even a few days before pulling the seedlings (20-25 d after seeding [DAS]). Late

spraying may kill RWM eggs laid in the seedbed before transplanting. Perhaps RWM control by foliar sprays after transplanting is inadequate because of seedbed infestation.

RWM eggs were monitored at 3d intervals from 7 to 24 DAS on 50 randomly selected plants 0, 10, 20, 30, 100, 130, 150 cm from the edges of 7 farmers' seedbeds. Wooden planks were set over the seedbeds so plants could be

removed without disturbing the rest of the seedbed.

Most eggs were laid on the edges of seedbeds (Fig. 1), which indicates that RWM is attracted to the open standing water around seedbeds (Fig. 2a) but will lay a few eggs in the closed canopies of seedbeds, on direct-seeded lowland rice, or on plants growing over azolla.

Central Luzon farmers leave the deep-rooted seedlings along the edges of